

Assessment of Nurses' Practices Regarding Ethical Issues Toward Patients in Critical Care Unit Select Government Hospital in Khartoum State, Sudan. Descriptive Study

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Abstract

Background:

Ethics deal with standards of conduct and moral judgment. Nursing is a profession that care for personal and private aspects of people's lives. Therefore, nurses need to know the basic ethical aspects of nursing which is integral in nursing practices.

Objectives:

To assess Nurse's practice regarding ethical issues towards patients in critical care units in governmental hospitals -Khartoum state in Sudan.

Method:

A descriptive cross sectional research design was used to conduct the study. Simple random sampling method was adopted to select 125 nurses working in governmental hospitals-Khartoum state from 2023-2024 it included 125 nurses. nurses practice regarding ethical issue to ward patient Self-administered structured observation checklists was used for data collection and analyzed using IBM SPSS Version 25. Descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, Chi-square test was used to analyze the data

Result:

The findings revealed that 59.2% of nurses had adequate practice level of patients care ethics. There was significant association between nurses practice level with age and years of experiences (p value= 0.05 and 0.008 respectively)..

Conclusion:

The study concluded adequate level of practice among nurses at selected hospitals in Khartoum state. Nurses' practice of patient care ethics should be upgraded through educational and awareness programs.

Recommendations:

Improving the quality of nursing practice should focus more studies to be conducted to improve nurses' level of practice regarding ethical issues in nursing, so that proper intervention can be implemented.

KEYWORDS:

Critical care, Ethical issue ,Nursing practice ,critical ,Sudan.

1.INTRODUCTION:

Nursing is essentially concerned with the care of vulnerable fellow human being, patients view nurses as skilled companions who discern the care needs of patients, wanting to provide these needs in a professional fashion ⁽¹⁾

When nursing curriculum sufficiently addresses ethics, providing nurses with the tools to help them reflect critically on what nursing care implies, nursing education can contribute to the development of nurses as skilled companions. By stimulating critical reflection on nursing practice, nursing ethics education aim to encourage a virtuous attitude in nurses, forming the basis from which to provide good care .in line with Toronto's ideas, that express an attitude of caring ⁽²⁾. The essence of nursing is the precise integration of expert activity (knowledge and skills) and caring (virtue); nursing can therefore be amoral practice ⁽³⁾.

There are several approaches to ethics education for nurses:

The first consists of introducing nurses to the principles of right action. Examples of such principle can be found in codes of ethics for nurse's nondiscrimination, confidentiality, and informed consent.

How nursing care be provided is described in codes of ethics by means of normative principal s specific for nurse's practice ⁽⁴⁾. These principles typically focus mainly on nurse's acts and not on the nurses as persons or their attitudes. This approach defines which action are morally right and which are wrong, characteristics of actions that tend to make these actions right ^(5- 6).

The second approach proposed by van Hooff consist of a virtue ethics approach to ethics education and places greater emphasis on the attitude of caring as a starting point of good nursing care ⁽⁴⁾ . In van Hooff's' view, teaching ethics to nurses is not just about teaching conformity to codes or how to avoid litigation; it is about empowering nurses to act in difficult or stressful situation in which objective guidelines are not available. ⁽⁴⁾

Ethical values are essential for any healthcare provider. Ethics comes from the Greek word "ethos," meaning character. Ethical values are universal rules of conduct that provide a practical basis for identifying what kinds of actions, intentions, and motives are valued. (7) Ethics are moral principles that govern how the person or a group will behave or conduct themselves.

The focus pertains to the right and wrong of actions and encompasses the decision-making process of determining the ultimate consequences of those actions. (8) Each person has their own set of personal ethics and morals. Ethics within healthcare are important because workers must recognize healthcare dilemmas, make good

judgments and decisions based on their values while keeping within all healthcare professionals, must have regulation and guidance within the profession. (9)

The American Nurses Association (ANA) has developed the Code of Ethics for this purpose.

Healthcare workers have a duty to refrain from maltreatment, minimize harm, and promote good towards patients. (10) This duty of treatment describing beneficence. Healthcare workers demonstrate this by providing a balance of benefits against risks to the patient. Assisting patients with tasks that they are unable to perform on their own, keeping side rails up for fall precautions, or providing medications in a quick and timely manner are all examples of beneficence.

All patients have a right to be treated fair and equally by others. Justice involves how people are treated when their interest competes with others. (11).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

General Objective:

The general objective of this study is to assess Nurse's practice regarding ethical issues towards patients in critical care units in governmental hospitals - Khartoum state.

Specific objectives:

To assess nurse's practice regarding ethical issues in critical patients.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1 Study design

A Descriptive, cross-sectional hospital -based study was conducted during the period (July 2022 - July 2023) .

2. 2 Study area

The study was conducted in governmental Hospitals in Khartoum State which included: Alshaab teaching hospital (n=30), Ombadah Elnamozagy teaching hospital (n=15), Omdurman teaching hospital (n=17), Bahri teaching hospital (n=18), Khartoum teaching hospital (n=18), Ibrahim malik hospital (n=12) and Ahmed Gasim hospital (n=15). the study was done in critical care units.

Khartoum State

Khartoum State is one of the eighteen States of Sudan. Although it is the smallest state by area (22,142 km²), it is the most populous state in Sudan - 7,993,900 in 2018. It contains the country's largest city by population, Omdurman, together with the towns of North Khartoum and Khartoum; Khartoum City is the national capital of Sudan. It contains state offices, governmental and non-governmental organizations, cultural institutions, and the main airport. The city is located in the Central of Sudan at the confluence of the White Nile and the Blue Nile, where the two rivers unite to form the River Nile. The confluence of the two rivers creates a unique effect. The state lies between longitudes 31.5 to 34°E and latitudes 15 to 16°N.7-09-13 (12).

.2.3 Study Population

The study targeted all nurses working in critical care units in the study area according to criteria of selection.

2.3.1 Inclusion criteria:

The nurses recruited in the study included those who:

- Nurses who are working for more than 6 months
- Willing to participate in the Study.
- Nurses with diploma and above.

2.3.2 Exclusion Criteria:

Nurses who were excluded from the study included those:

- Non-Sudanese nurses
- Nurses in an internship period
- non-permanent contract.

2.4 Sample size and Sample technique.

2.4.1 Sample size:

The researcher was selecting the sample for all nurses how fulfil the above criteria in critical care unit at governmental hospitals in Khartoum state.

2.4.2 Sample technique

The study was total enumeration research hence there was total coverage purposive size.

2.5 Study Variables

Available is characteristics or quality that take one different value for example it varies from one person or object to another.

2.5.1 Independent Variable:

The independent variable include (age ,gender , education , experience.).

2.5.2 Dependent Variable

Dependent Variable means the variable hypothesized to depend on or be caused by another variable (the independent variable) in this study. the dependent Variables practice of the nurses regarding ethical issues in critical care unit.

2.6 Data Collection instrument

The data collection instrument consists of two sections as follow:

2.6.1 section one

The first part of the tool related to demographic characteristics of the nurses such as age, gender, education, experience.

2.6.2 section two

twelve observation checklists about ethical aspects Practice in critical care unit.

2.6.2.1 Scoring Interpretation of practice by using Likert Scale scoring.

practice checklist consisted of 12 items, if the item is done it was given a score of 'one' and if not done it was given a score of „zero“.

>75% Adequate practice ,51-75% Moderate practice, ≤50% Inadequate practice.

2.8 Validity of the Questionnaire

The Questionnaire for data collection was designed from literature review and presented to the supervisor and other experts in the field of research and ethics that ensured the face, some modification have been made, content and construct validity before it was used for the study.

2.9 Reliability of Tool

A Pilot study was conducted to assess study tools clarity and applicability. It has also served in estimating the time needed for fulfilling the study tools. The revised questionnaires were piloted to investigate the feasibility of data collection tools. Collecting pilot study data lasts for one week. No modification had occurred in the pilot study so it was included in the main study subject.

2.10 Ethical consideration

Approval from the Karari university faculty of graduate studies & scientific research is done. involved official parties like state ministry of health.

Research committee and administration of the hospitals will be informed about data collection and the aims of the research. verbal informed consent will be requested from all respondents to participate in the study after fully explaining the research purpose and objectives in the simple words. Names of the respondents will not be used in the report . the questionnaire will be filled out during their rest time.

confidentiality of the information gathered will be assured. respondents have a right to withdraw at any time during the research, however, their right to refuse to participate in the study will be respected and they will not lose the right to any benefits from the research . all necessary precautions and precautionary measures for covid -19 in the hospitals will be followed.

3. Result

Figure 4.1: Frequency distribution of age among Study Subjects (n=125)

Figure 4.2: Frequency distribution of Gender among Study Subjects (n=125)

Figure 4.3: Frequency distribution of Education among Study Subjects (n=125)

Figure 4.4: Frequency distribution of Years of Experiences among Study Subjects (n=125)

Figure 4.5: Frequency distribution of working place among Study Subjects (n=125)

Figure 4.6: Frequency distribution of Work Units among Study Subjects (n=125)

4.2 Practice assessment

Table 4.1: The mean score of Practice items of Ethical Issues as reported by Study participants (n=125).

No	Practice items	Done		Not done	
		N	%	N	%
1	Communication with patients	101	80.8	24	19.2
2	Patients Privacy	116	92.8	9	7.2
3	Share information with patients & family	66	52.8	59	46.2
4	Patient confidentiality	100	80.0	25	20
5	Respect patient	110	88.0	15	12.0
6	Patient's rights	77	61.6	48	38.4
7	The dignity of the patients	107	85.6	17	13.6
8	Take consent from the patients before any procedure	68	54.4	57	45.6
9	Hygiene for patient	107	85.6	18	14.4
10	Use safety measures to prevent patients	108	86.4	17	13.6
11	Self-care monitoring	96	76.8	29	23.2
12	Nutritional for patient	115	92.0	10	8.0

Discussion

Ethics plays a vital role in primary healthcare, and it is a skill that primary care physician must master because they are the first line of patient conflict. While dealing with the professional ethics, it is important to focus on the nurses' practice. The current study attempts to answer the questions of how much the nurses are knowledgeable about patient care ethics focusing on ethical principle, to what extent they are practicing in clinical practice, and whether their practice is correlated and influenced by their socio-demographic and job-related variables.

In the present study, 51.2% of participants below to the age group of 31-40 years with 1-3 years of professional experience (31.2%), 51.2% were males, 64.8% had a professional of bachelor's in nursing and (24%) of the participants work in Alshaab Teaching hospital. Our report is supported by a study done at Punjab^[43] found that 96.67% of the participants were male, 73.33% of the staff below to the age group of 25-45 years, 68% were B.Sc. holders and 64.67% of them were with 0-5years experience.

This study further reveals that 59.2% of the study nurses have adequate level of practice of patient care ethics. This finding is like findings of the study conducted at governmental hospital in Egypt (13). This conveys that the practice of study nurses is better than their knowledge. On contrary, a study conducted in a teaching hospital in Bhairahawa, Nepal (14). found that only half (50%) of nurses had an adequate practice of nursing ethics and law. This discrepancy can be because of nurses working in government hospital had long working experience and exposure than that of private hospital nurses which refines practice with repeated exposure.

Regarding the relation between nurses' practice of professional ethics and their personal and job characteristics, there was statistically significant relation evident between nurses' practice about professional ethics with age & years of experience. This could be explained that age plays a significant role with nurses' practice regarding ethics by an accumulation of experience. In this context, a Niger Study (15). asserted that years of experience had noticeable effects on nurses' knowledge and practice about legal and ethical aspects of nursing practice. Moreover, in Indian Study (16). found a statistically significant relation between nurses' practice about ethics and their age and working experience. Knowledge in ethics has been shown to enhance nursing practice in identification of ethical questions within practical problems, development of innovative solutions for prevalent problems and development of sound ethical beliefs and practices (17). In this context, the results of the present study pointed out that there is significant association between nurses' knowledge and practice regarding ethics issues. This finding was harmonious with study at Mansoura University Hospital (18). confirmed that that professional practice of nursing ethics has a deep and organic relationship with nursing knowledge and nursing values and intervention(19).

5.2 Conclusion

The findings of this study conclude that the nurse with satisfactory and adequate level of practice are more than the nurses with unsatisfactory and inadequate level of practice about patient care ethics.

Nurses' practice is influence by job related characteristics like years of experiences, while their knowledge is not influence by those characteristics.

5.3 Recommendations

- Creating awareness regarding code of ethics, ethical principles and standards of nursing practice in clinical areas.
- Nursing syndicate should have an effective role in regular monitoring and evaluating nurses' performance regarding ethical behavior to ensure its application through following specific evaluation sheet for professional ethics.

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